

Thymosin Alpha-1 (T α 1)

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Abstract

Thymosin α_1 (T α -1) is a naturally occurring polypeptide in the thymus gland that is recognized for modifying, enhancing, and restoring immune function. It is commonly used as an immune enhancer in viral infectious diseases such as hepatitis B, hepatitis C, and acquired immune deficiency syndrome (AIDS). In this review, I discuss key literature on the structure, enzymatic action and isoelectric point of T α -1 along with its biological significance in humans.

Introduction

The thymus gland is a small, specialized lymphoid organ in the immune system, vital for its function in the generation of T-cells, which are used against pathogen invasion and sustaining immune function. Thymosin α -1 (T α -1) is a naturally occurring thymic peptide derived from prothymosin alpha and was the first peptide to be isolated from thymic tissue by Goldstein *et al* in 1977^[1].

So far, researchers have found that T α 1 is a highly conserved peptide hormone that is extensively found in thymus, spleen, lung, kidney, brain, and blood, with the largest concentration in the thymus. T α 1 has long been recognized as an immune enhancing and immune restoring agent; thus, it has been used in various clinical and research settings. It is extensively used in fighting numerous infections, such as HIV, mold toxicity, sepsis and recently in severely ill coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) patients. The synthetic derivative of T α 1, thymalfasin, is used in various clinical products for the treatment of hepatitis B and C in developing countries, as well as immune boosting effects in variety of other disorders.

Overview of T α 1 and its uses

Thymosin proteins are typically short (28-50 amino acids), positively charged, and inherently unregulated peptides (i.e., their activity is not subject to sophisticated internal biological systems that alter their function in response to feedback from subsequent responses).

There are currently three distinct ways in which bioactive T α 1 can be obtained:

1. isolation from calf thymuses.
2. solid-phase synthesis, which is a purely chemical way of peptide synthesis and is currently the only method accepted for production of T α 1 for clinical use.
3. from either prokaryotic organism such as *Escherichia coli*, or eukaryotic organisms such as yeast.

Thymosin alpha-1 has a wide variety of biological uses that range from immune-modulating to anti-tumour properties.

The immune response of T α 1 is due to its action in elevating the activity of T cell maturation into CD4+/CD8+ T cells. It is also quite successful in limiting tumour growth; hence, it is used in the treatment of various cancers.

Structure and Isoelectric point of T α 1

The sequences of the T α 1 peptide are as follows: Ac-Ser-Asp-Ala-Ala-Val-Asp-Thr-Ser-Ser-Glu-Ile-Thr-Thr-Lys-Asp-Leu-Lys-Glu-Lys-Lys-Glu-Val-Val-Glu-Glu-Ala-Glu-Asn-OH.

To calculate the isoelectric point, we identify the ionizable groups:

- C-terminus: $pK_a \sim 2.34$
- Aspartic acid (Asp): $pK_a \sim 3.90$
- Glutamic acid (Glu): $pK_a \sim 4.25$
- Lysine (Lys): $pK_a \sim 10.54$

The isoelectric point was estimated by averaging the pKa values around the neutral charge.

Clearly, $pI = (3.90 + 4.20) / 2 = 4.05$, or at $pH = 4.05$, $T\alpha 1$ exists predominantly in zwitter ion form.

Key points from this discussion are:

1. It is an acidic peptide with an isoelectric point of 4.05.
2. The terminus N of $T\alpha 1$ is acetylated.
3. There are no disulphide bonds or glycosylation structures.

Non-Enzymatic Nature of $T\alpha 1$

Thymosin α -1 is non-enzymatic in nature. It functions primarily as a protein that eases immune responses rather than acting as an enzyme that catalyses specific reactions.

Biological consequences of the removal of $T\alpha 1$ from human body

Thymosin α -1 engages in immune regulation, enhancing immune responses and T-cell maturation. It also plays a critical role in the control of inflammation, immunity, and tolerance. Due to its aid in the production of T-cell dependent antibodies, it's also used as a vaccine adjuvant for increasing the effectiveness of certain vaccines. Recently, in certain ongoing human trails, $T\alpha$ -1 has also been proposed to be an effective supplement for patients suffering from SARS-CoV-2 (especially those with compromised immunity due to severe lymphocytopenia).

If $T\alpha$ -1 were removed from the human body, several significant biological impacts will follow, primarily due to compromised function of the immune system. Firstly, as a direct consequence to the removal of $T\alpha$ -1, the body's ability to fight even mild infections would be significantly compromised, leaving individuals highly vulnerable to infections. Secondly, following the absence of $T\alpha$ -1, there would be crippled T-cell antibody maturation and response, which would potentially cause recurring infections and reduced vaccine efficiency.

Additionally, as we earlier talked about the anti-inflammatory properties of $T\alpha$ -1; with those missing, there could be an increase in inflammatory and autoimmune disorders, where the body attacks its own internal biological systems. The absence of $T\alpha$ -1 would also lead to increased risk of tumour development as it limits tumour growth.

Summing up, Thymosin α -1 is gravely important for proper immune function and anti-cancer defence. Its absence would probably cause immune dysregulation, infection risks and heightened risk of cancer, thus making it important for sustaining a healthy life.

References

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